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Dynamics of personal identity: the role of internal and external factors

Personal identity is a complex and multilayered system in which an individual interacts with both their internal world and significant aspects of the surrounding environment. At its core is a sense of self-coherence, reflecting an awareness of the unity of various aspects of the «self». Identity is formed based on components through which a person perceives the world, structures their knowledge, and describes themselves. As a result, personal identity consists of multiple identifications, each representing an individual's connection to a specific aspect of the external world and its perception within a unified perceptual system.

Communication and self-communication play a crucial role in this process. It is worth noting that long before the advent of mass communications and digital technologies, humans were already deeply communicative beings. This capacity for communication underpinned the formation of personal identity. Interaction with others provides us with external «reference points» necessary for identification, highlighting the importance of social interactions. With the development of modern technologies, the ways in which individuals construct their identity have undergone significant changes, becoming increasingly complex [1]. The expansion of communicative space and the increase in the number of interactions within mass media and the internet lead to the complexity and instability of personal identity. To maintain its stability, individuals are compelled to sustain multiple communicative connections constantly. As a result, modern personal identity takes on a networked nature, representing a complex structure of interactions with others, the world, and oneself.

Social theories emphasize that personality is shaped not only through innate predispositions and unique life experiences but also through social interactions. Through communication with various social groups, socialization occurs, leading to

the formation of collective identifications – such as national, ethnic, civic, and political. These identifications play a key role in integrating personal and social identity, creating a broad context for self-understanding. Alongside broad collective identifications, there are also narrower, personal identifications formed through specific interactions.

Communication, social connections, and the ability to express oneself through language occupy a central place in this complex and multilayered interaction. Each social connection, whether real or imagined, creates a unique identification. It can be based on relationships with real people or on imaginary characters that become part of an individual's internal world as significant «others» or alter egos. These characters can serve as role models that individuals orient their behavior towards. An individual's ability to express their inner states through discourse is one of the key characteristics of self-awareness [2; 3]. Research shows that awareness of one's uniqueness is closely related to the increase in autobiographical texts. The ability to verbalize one's identity reflects the maturity of self-awareness and plays a central role in the formation of personal identity, which is most clearly expressed through the self-narrative. This process allows for not only an awareness of but also a constructive expression of one's understanding of oneself and one's place in the world. Thus, the formation of personal identity represents a dynamic process where internal and external factors intertwine.

Human consciousness inevitably strives to resolve contradictions, which can be observed in the phenomenon of cognitive dissonance, where individuals attempt to align their beliefs and behavior. In this context, individuals also strive to create a coherent and consistent model of their identity. In contemporary times, self-presentation on the Internet is a vivid confirmation of these efforts. However, despite the significance of the narrative approach, it still cannot encompass the entire complexity of personal identity. No online representation, no matter how detailed, can reflect every aspect of a person.

This internal communication finalizes the formation of identity, enabling individuals to integrate different aspects of themselves into a cohesive whole.

Naturally, the people around us also play a significant role in shaping our identity. However, ultimately, it is our own perception of us that remains the main factor in shaping personal identity. Often, others attribute traits to us that we do not see in ourselves. Our own perception of ourselves can differ significantly from how others see us [4]. Even those closest to us, who know us best, may see only a part of who we truly are, while the full picture remains hidden from everyone.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the completeness of personal identity is achieved through a complex interplay of internal self-perception and external evaluations. The dynamics of identity represent a process in which internal and external factors intertwine. Identity is formed through interaction with both the inner world and the surrounding environment, where communication and self-communication play crucial roles. Social interactions and self-expression through language contribute to the creation of both collective and personal identifications. In the modern world, internet representations only partially reflect personality, and a comprehensive understanding is possible only through the integration of various perspectives.

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